

ROLE OF THE HUMAN RESOURCE OFFICER, STRATEGIC PLANNING, WORK ENGAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN CAGAYAN DE ORO CITY: A CAUSAL MODEL

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 3

Pages: 443-455

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2359

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13771795

Manuscript Accepted: 07-23-2024

Role of the Human Resource Officer, Strategic Planning, Work Engagement, and Organizational Performance in Cagayan De Oro City: A Causal Model

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Abstract

Challenges and trials in HR require everything that deals with being a person to anyone and any office. This study aimed to contribute to the field of human services management as well as to business and management by measuring the process of organizational learning, work engagement, and the role of HR officers in HSOs in Cagayan de Oro City to be backed up with the best model when dealing with its staff and faculty regarding organizational performance. The study used descriptive correlational and causal-comparative designs. Two hundred fifty-five respondents were full-time staff and faculty in the selected higher institutions in the city. A researcher's survey questionnaire was used to gather the data and identify the influence of the variables. Results revealed that the respondents' answers were highly aware, very highly implemented, very highly engaged, and very highly performed when dealing with the organizational performance of HEIs, showing causal model 3 is the best-fit model for organizational performance. It is concluded that the environment plays a vital role in the level of awareness of the role of human resource officers, where improvements in the hiring process must be thoroughly evaluated, leading to the organizational performance of the higher education institutions. It is recommended that the administration encourage the HR officer to propose a continuous development of emotional intelligence programs and seminars to improve the social-emotional awareness of the employees, leading to well-developed self-control and interpersonal skills, which are vital to the organizational performance of institutions.

Keywords: *role of human resource officer, strategic planning, work engagement, organizational performance in higher education institution*

Introduction

Being in the field of Human Resources before, concerned individuals were able to see the broadness of the work of it. Challenges and/or trials in the field are not easy tasks to be solved. It requires everything which deals with being a person to anyone, and to any office.

According to Coursera (2024), human resource management, or HRM, involves coordinating, managing, and allocating human capital, or employees, in ways that move an organization's goals forward. HRM focuses on investing in employees, ensuring their safety, and managing all aspects of staffing, from hiring to compensation and development. The purpose of human resource management (HRM) is to take the necessary steps to implement part of the management task, which depends on some aspects of teachers' activities, specifically in terms of teachers' training, evaluating performance, rewarding and creating a healthy and fair environment for the managers that includes a range of different activities and its purpose is to gather all data and processes of an organization in a unit system and eventually improving the performance of organization and other institutions. Using scheduling systems is a must because each manager wishes to be aware of the status of all resources and assets of the organization in a short time and with high precision; in this way, making decisions and taking the decisions will be in a good process.

Organizational Learning (OL) has been identified in business administration and management studies over the past forty years as a means of growth, efficiency, and competitive advantage for organizations. Broadly, OL aims to explain organizational changes that promote strategic renewal (Lee et al., 2015). This perspective assigns causal importance to linkages between cognition and action and vice versa, manifested at many organizational management levels.

The importance of HRM to any business success in any context has been widely recognized and deserves continued research. Research shows that many HRM practices can potentially improve and sustain organizational performance (Albrecht et al., 2015). The strategic HRM literature shows that human and social capital are knowledge constructs that could be developed or modified via HRM practices. In this regard, a significant task of managers is to develop HRM initiatives to generate and refine intellectual capital assets and improve innovation capacity and organizational performance. Consequently, research that involves strategic issues and uses the organizational learning perspective remains underdeveloped. This is probably due to the ontological and epistemological struggle that blurs the learning perspective in the strategic research agenda.

Previous research has demonstrated that employee work engagement can enhance their participation and stimulate their best performance, thus supporting organizational goals (Wang et al., 2017). Work engagement is a condition whereby an individual has a positive and fulfilling attitude toward their duties, characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption. In this context, vigor is defined as a high level of energy while working. In contrast, dedication is denoted as solid involvement in one's work, and absorption refers to being concentrated and happy while working (Schaufeli, 2017).

Reasoning in this way, the researcher will conduct a qualitative case study of the growth strategy of a local company in the education industry in 2021. Specifically, this research examined the relationship between organizational levels, learning processes, and strategic activities.

This study contributes to the field of human services management as well as to business and management by measuring the process of organizational learning, work engagement, and the role of HR officers in HSOs. It also contributes to social work education and macro social work practice by examining an essentially, business and management concept and applying it to social work. The study has a practical and academic/theoretical application, with relatively limited exploration of organizational learning, work engagement, and the role of HR officers in the field of social work. The literature on variables mentioned leans heavily towards pointing out the benefit of an organization's success in improving performance if the organization is learning. For this study, the size of educational institutions is further defined according to the management process. In small institutions, managers can supervise personnel individually from the central office to the rank-and-file level. While one or more levels of management may exist, it is not necessary to use a middle manager to accomplish routine management activities. Medium institutions are managed through one management level, and large institutions are managed through two or more levels of management.

Research Questions

This study aimed to know the role of the human resource officer, strategic planning, work engagement, and organizational performance in the selected schools in Cagayan de Oro City.

1. Is there a significant relationship between the organizational performance and:
 - 1.1. role of human resource officer;
 - 1.2. strategic planning; and
 - 1.3. work engagement?
2. Which among the variables, singly or in combination, influence the organizational performance?

Literature Review

Roles of Human Resource Officer

Human Resource Management (HRM) entails a broad spectrum of responsibilities and functions to efficiently oversee an organization's human capital. Often referred to as the backbone of an organization, HRM plays a pivotal role in managing its most valuable asset—its people. The roles and functions of HRM are multifaceted, encompassing various aspects of the employee lifecycle and organizational growth. From recruitment and training to performance management and employee relations, HRM is integral to achieving business objectives and maintaining optimal workplace conditions (Bakkah, 2024).

Moreover, many researchers have explored the changing roles of HR managers. Some of them advocated that with this transition, the HR function is also transforming, writing on “transitions” in human resource management during the closing decades of the last century, researchers pointed out several key developments, but most especially a detectable shift in traditional and specialist area of HRM towards a broader concern with the strategic nature an impact on the HR role (Ahmad, 2017).

Furthermore, HRM or personnel management revolves around effectively managing an organization's human capital, namely its employees. This encompasses many tasks, including talent acquisition, onboarding, training and development, performance management, compensation and benefits administration, employee relations, and ensuring compliance with labor laws and regulations. HRM entails a comprehensive approach to managing and nurturing an organization's workforce. These functions, which include talent acquisition, training and development, performance management, compensation and benefits, employee relations, and policy development, collectively contribute to the management and development of an organization's human capital (Bonifacio, 2024).

Hiring Process

Identifying and assessing candidates for employment are primarily managerial decision-making processes. Negotiations regarding compensation usually involve multiple stakeholders: the candidate, the hiring manager, and the HR department. Once a candidate is chosen, the hiring manager will notify HR. An HR representative will then draft an initial offer, incorporating input from the hiring manager and assessing the candidate's qualifications, ensuring it aligns with the job's designated salary range (Newman et al., 2016).

Moreover, according to Rivera (2015), the perceived value of job analysis, which was historically a fundamental aspect of organizational human resources (HR) practices, has significantly diminished recently. This decline can be attributed partly to the belief among managers that jobs evolve too rapidly for analysis to remain relevant. Additionally, hiring managers often rely on intuition or “gut feeling” rather than utilizing available reliable evaluation tools.

Moreover, Travis (2015) mentioned that even though high priority is placed in the selection process in identifying the right candidate for the right job, many times, the organizations often are not happy with the selected candidates. Hiring mistakes surface, disappointments and regrets are felt by the management after a certain period. Primarily, the hiring process costs a lot for the organization and secondarily, it affects the smooth running of an organization and ultimately, the overall productivity is hindered

(Friedman, 2015; Travis, 2015). Therefore, apart from the traditional screening methods of selecting the resume and conducting interviews, organizations are looking for a more reliable screening and selection process with the help of psychological tests.

Indeed, this phenomenon can be elucidated as an ingrained neural process within the brain and nervous system, serving as the foundation for various cognitive and behavioral functions that operate instinctively. These functions encompass thought processes, memory, emotions, and motivation emanating from established neural pathways (Janetius & Mini, 2019).

However, a careful process of relationship building over time could ensure there are candidates when the need arises. As Konrad, Yang, and Maurer (2016) suggested, a strategic human resource management approach can complement a diversity and equality management program. As an outcome, understand where and how HR needs to be a strategic partner and where a continuous, back-and-forth information flow between HR and business units is required.

Cultural Growth

Kaura (2018) stated that informal social networks of people from different cultures are a common occurrence in the workplace, but little is known about their impact on employee productivity. As a result, some organizational leaders believe that these networks have negative consequences for an organization. The study, conversely, indicates that networks contribute positively to employee productivity. Managers should pay attention to other factors, such as employee diversity, which can impede employee productivity and encourage informal interactions. As a result, managers should value employee diversity, recognize the value of in-group identities, and use them to foster a positive work environment.

Additionally, the findings of Campbell's study (2015) shed light on various strategies business leaders employ to create and implement flexible work schedules and virtual work programs. These strategies include (a) advocating for a standard set of core working hours, (b) permitting flexible start and end times, (c) setting up remote office arrangements, (d) maximizing virtual communication tools, and (e) prioritizing employee quality of life. Given these insights, many business leaders are exploring novel work models.

Moreover, Deal and Peterson (2016) mentioned that a shared set of moral beliefs, reliance and a sense of responsibility, appreciation of employees, and commemoration of achievement are all attributed to Student performance. Culture affects all aspects of an educational institution, and it influences informal conversations between students.

Also, a positive school culture gives students a safe, accommodating, motivating, and challenging environment, and the school administrators have an essential role to play in the improvement and advancement of this (Confeld, 2016).

Additionally, Changsheng, et al. (2018) stated that individuals adjust to their environments with the help of their acquired social and emotional skills that play a crucial role in their lives. The importance of socio-emotional skills has risen significantly because it contributes to the well-being not just of individuals, but of the whole community and in an increasingly transforming and diverse world.

Moreover, Agarwal (2018) mentioned that by developing robust models to understand environmental trends and forecast how current unchecked practices will affect the natural environment, data scientists can present a well-reasoned, quantitative analysis and inspire people to be more engaged in sustainable and environment-friendly practices. Data scientists are uniquely poised to harness the power of patterns and tell compelling stories about nature. Statistical models might not be able to change people's reliance on technology, but they can certainly use that reliance to heighten our awareness of our natural environment. Finally, Burgess and Sievertsen (2020) mentioned that the central objective of attending or working in a school would be to boost the ability of a person, and that is why researchers say that school is one of the most important settings for the acquisition of skills.

Organizational Support

Varma and Russell (2016) attributed the practice to the organizational support theory which assumes that the employees have their own beliefs about the organization's attention and appreciation as well as its ability to support them if they help to achieve its goals successfully; basically, staff expects to receive support in specific situations. Accordingly, expected organizational support influences organizational commitment, career impact, career absorption and organizational performance; in addition to the desire not to leave the organization.

Also, in the point of view of Li, et al. (2015), training and development strategy is one of the most important jobs in the human resources department, particularly in economies based on knowledge.

Moreover, the study of Nadeem (2015) connected a few practices of human resources management, such as functional development, by emphasizing that the employee who receives organizational support from his organization will try to make more effort to be supported to develop himself functionally.

Moreover, the most recent Perceived Organization Support (POS) meta-analysis reported significant associations between POS and the perceived favorableness of a variety of human resource practices, including developmental opportunities and family-supportive organizational practices, as well as job conditions, including job enrichment conditions, role stressors, and benefits use (Kurtessis et al., 2017).

Likewise, Caesens et al. (2016) reported that change in indebtedness mediated the relationship between POS and proactive behavior

directed toward the organization, like making suggestions to improve organizational efficiency and improving organizational effectiveness.

Therefore, human resource management also needs to adapt to lift the skills level and work initiative of frontline workers to avoid the decline of production efficiency and product quality during the transition to flexible manufacturing (Prieto & Perez-Santana, 2014).

Strategic Planning

Abun Damianus (2021) emphasizes in his study that management is highly bureaucratic, and here are the elements of bureaucracy such as hierarchical authority, rules, division of labor performance-based promotion, efficiency, and impersonality (Reynolds, 2018). Though it has been recognized to improve efficiency, however, it has also been criticized for being impersonal and focusing on too many rules and procedures, which causes a delay in decision-making and responsiveness to the changes in the environment. Much of the time, managers are spent discussing internal issues. Within a bureaucratic environment, decision-making is centralized, and employees are not given the freedom to make decisions on their own (Hamel & Zanini, 2017).

For the record, Max Weber considered bureaucracy as the most efficient and rational way of managing large organizations such as the government through a systematic process and organizational structure to maintain order (Mulder, 2017).

Therefore, the modern definition of bureaucracy no longer refers to government organization alone but also refers to any form of organization. Nowadays, it simply means the rationalization of an organization marked by structure, formalized functions, and impersonality of human relations (Serpa & Ferreira, 2019).

Performance Analysis

Over the last couple of decades or so, researchers have devoted considerable empirical effort toward understanding the relationship between human resource management (HRM) and organizational outcomes (Bondarouk et al., 2016; Ogbonnaya & Valizade, 2016).

In recent years, globalization has surged, connecting economies worldwide through technological advancements and enhanced connectivity (Carnevale & Hatak, 2020).

This interlinking of economies has spurred foreign trade growth. Additionally, many companies heavily rely on their employees to maintain a competitive edge in the market. Consequently, the efficiency of human resources and its management has become paramount (Collins, 2021). It includes policies and practices set to improve organizational efficiency, engagement of employees and work quality (Khan & Abdullah, 2019).

Moreover, as highlighted by Hameed and Anwar (2018), HRM's activities significantly impact the entire compensation and selection process, underscoring its pivotal role within organizations. The capacity of HRM within an organization is closely linked to strategic HRM's management functions. Strategically, this implies that human resources management practices encompass policies addressing fundamental areas such as promoting workforce engagement, evaluation, knowledge application, capacity building, employee training, staff retention, and administration management (Singh et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, building on the research conducted by Abdullah & Othman (2016), it becomes evident that organizational success is intricately tied to the effectiveness of HR management practices. Furthermore, as highlighted by Anwar (2017), selective hiring practices not only impact organizational performance but also contribute positively to it.

Furthermore, research conducted by Hanić and Jevtić (2020) revealed a significant correlation between effective human resource management, including management training and employee compensation, and an organization's overall performance.

Additionally, Pham et al. (2020) discussed scholars' exploration of the relationship between management rewards and risk-taking, highlighting a solid association between the two. This association is believed to have a positive impact on outcomes. The researchers from these studies have commendably documented the influence of rewards in their literature reviews.

Lastly, according to Westerman (2020), there are two varieties of incentives: monetary ones, such as bonuses, allowance, or rewards, or in addition to that, a lot of praise is bestowed on those who give an effort and reward themselves public recognition of their effort by making a special effort and having an extra day off for what they have done.

Develop Marketing

Wu et al. (2020) and Elifoglu et al. (2018) mentioned that effective advertising and marketing could display the USP of the organization and attract specific customers, which is the job of the marketing team which can be done with efficient employees.

Not to mention, saving time, effort, and money can be done by efficient management of human resources with the integration of cloud technology (Abdullah et al., 2020; Yin et al., 2019).

With this, the manager's attention is essential in providing training to the employees to accelerate the organization's performance, providing proper training to the employees is an effective strategy of HRM (Ozkoser 2019 and; Yamada et al., 2022).

In like manner, Alshehri et al. (2021) and VanScoy et al. (2018) mentioned that one can accelerate the performance of the marketing organization, and cross-cultural design in the workplace environment can be a procedure to strategically manage human resources.

Equally, the innovation cluster personnel management appears the foundation of any economic system, as employees and people are the most valuable resource of the country (Sergeevich & Vladimirovich, 2015; Kunelbayev et al., 2016) and cluster enterprises. Social relations, production volumes, technology, and other factors determine content management personnel.

Likewise, in the conditions of the modern economic market, the role of innovative processes that make up the production of the organization's activity sharply increases. It is necessary to activate all the existing provisions in this area, including the management areas of the cluster innovative potential that had previously been given enough attention (Oleinikova et al., 2016).

Furthermore, today, especially present, is the question of the teacher's training capable to provide such training and the development of programs focused on updating and synthesis experience and knowledge that are trained (Belizón et al., 2016).

Studies by Cable et al. (2013) suggest that employee orientation should focus more on employees and not so much on organizations because allowing them to develop their self-identity and self-expression at work has been found to make them more satisfied. However, employees should be encouraged to express themselves in ways that are consistent with the brand image of the company.

Track Progress

Melo et al. (2019) mentioned that focusing on the relationship between internal and external circumstances encouraging lifelong learning within specific companies helps gain an insight into the relative role that public policy and public economic incentives can play in shaping employers' investment and employees' attitudes towards lifelong learning.

Moreover, Black (2023) stated that the study of mentorship models in veterans' affairs hospital pre-doctoral training emphasized that mentorship of doctoral-level psychology interns may provide an opportunity to aid in the MISSION Act's retention efforts. The purpose of this study was to look into the differences in retention rates between VA internships that provide Formal Mentorship Programs (FMPs) and VA internships that do not offer FMPs (mentorship via supervision only). The relationship between the total domains of formal mentoring (communication, mentoring process, mentee development, mentor, and program efficacy) and retention was also evaluated. The findings show that there is no significant difference in retention rates between VA sites (FMP vs. no FMP) and that there is no significant relationship between the number of FMP domains and retention.

Furthermore, Lee (2017) highlighted that there is awareness of the potential for leaders to understand better predictors of involuntary turnover and the potential to save money on recruitment and training. Better employee retention strategies may help business owners become more profitable; these findings may also contribute to the body of knowledge for stable employment opportunities.

Benjamin et al. (2022) stated that improved team function and performance are associated with leadership, supportive team behavior, communication, and performance feedback across various sectors. Addressing the reported challenges and considering the importance of organizational commitment to team development can help ensure that team objectives are effectively designed, delivered, and sustained in complex sporting organizations where leaders must respond to multiple stakeholders and meet performance goals across various dimensions of effectiveness.

Work Engagement

Shusha et al. (2016) mentioned in their study that one could claim that among the reasons behind employee 'disengagement' is inadequate managerial practices, in which staff lack good professional relations with their supervisors and are left without a chance to express their opinions and participate in decision-making, not to mention obtaining relevant information from those supervisors. Employees need to see their managers caring about and committed to the organization. Only then can managers attract employees to put outstanding efforts into their work.

Despite the fact that, even though, work and employee engagement are being taught in several managerial subjects as important organizational topics, the definition and underpinnings of engagement are yet poorly understood. The authors note that proper understanding of work engagement in the higher education (HE) service sector is required to enhance employee and student performance, in addition to other HE organizations' performance-related results (Abdelkader et al., 2016).

Also, work engagement studies have expanded as researchers across the globe attempt to establish country-specific antecedents and consequences of engagement to enable organizations to succeed. Supervisors in most organizations are in a strategic position to make or break employees' determination and motivation to perform. Engagement at work still lacks a unified definition and measurement, in addition to a poor understanding of its conceptualizations. Notably, several studies support the assumed positive association between engagement at work and desired organizational performance (Shusha et al., 2016).

Physical Engagement

The focus was on two aspects of customer-employee interactions that contribute to the hospitality work environment for employees: customer-employee exchange and diverse customers. Previous research has identified customer-employee exchange as a crucial element of social exchange within the hospitality industry, showing a positive relationship between organizational citizenship behavior

and innovation behavior (Li & Hsu, 2016).

Likewise, while there is an abundance of research that has revealed that employees can be motivated by extrinsic rewards, there is scarce literature on the effect of intrinsic motivation driven by employee-customer interactions (Lee et al., 2015),

Moreover, Subramanya and Pugh's (2015) review only indicated the research published in management and applied psychology journals where customer-related variables (e.g., customer satisfaction, service performance) were treated as outcomes, as opposed to the larger body of studies outside of management, and those exploring customer-to-employee relationships.

Similarly, Groth and associates (2019) acknowledge that they approach their "review of reviews" of moments of truth in service "primarily from the perspective of management and organizational psychology and provide a review of selective theoretical contributions and empirical studies that have significantly shaped the quickly evolving service research literature within these subfields."

Additionally, Kumar and Pansari (2016) found that employee engagement predicted customer engagement and that customer engagement (a proximal predictor) is a better predictor of firm performance than employee engagement (a distal predictor).

Further, meta-analytic evidence suggests that ability EI is a significant predictor of supervisor-rated job performance (Joseph et al., 2015), hinting at the promise of emotional ability and competence-based constructs in predicting FLE behavioral outcomes. Furthermore, it was suggested that customers' and employees' enjoyment of the interactions mediate the relationship between customer participation in service and customer satisfaction.

Research related to customer incivility and customer mistreatment, defined as low-quality interpersonal interactions that FLEs receive from customers during service interactions, has been driven by two theoretical perspectives, namely, conservation of resource (COR) theory and justice theory (Koopmann et al., 2015).

Cognitive Engagement

It was mentioned that around 3 - 4% due to the increasing demand from the growing population (Statistics B of Labor, 2020). However, many researchers (Dos Santos, 2016; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2017) indicate that teachers are more likely to leave their teaching position and even quit the teaching profession every year due to stress, workload, financial considerations, and responsibilities (Weiner & Jerome, 2016). Due to the unbalanced student-teacher ratio, the teacher human resources shortage remains the main issue for school human resource management.

Furthermore, for nearly half a century, school human resource management and teacher shortages have been a serious problem (Weiner & Jerome, 2016). However, despite increasing level of academic literature conceptualizing the correlations between green HRM and employee workplace green behavior, this linkage has thus far not been adequately empirically examined. Moreover, past workplace green behavior studies have mainly explored the effect of organizational sustainability programs.

Emotional Engagement

To explore this area and address a call raised built from the strategic management literature to explore how bundles of HR practices enhance emotional labor, ultimately influencing emotional performance (i.e., emotional displays that are congruent with organizational expectations. Most models of emotional labor entail a three-part process involving emotional display rules, emotion regulation, and emotional displays (Grandey & Gabriel, 2015).

To date, there has only been a limited research examination on how HRM practices influence individual and organizational outcomes through employee engagement. Likewise, the researcher found that studies have dealt with emotional intelligence from certain aspects related to students and its relationship to the level of achievement, such as Al-Harassi and Michael (2019) and Al-Mawalia, et al. (2019).

The Emotional Competence Inventory scale was designed by Mickey Boyatz and Goleman. It is used to measure emotional intelligence in the work environment. The scale consists of (110) items that measure (20) competencies distributed over the four dimensions of emotional intelligence contained in the Goleman model (AzZo'bi, 2018; Zureigat et al., 2023; Az-Zo'bi et al., 2022).

Lastly, people may use adaptability to deal with current and expected career development tasks, as well as their coping mechanisms in complex, work-related professional and job transitions, where adaptability helps control anxiety through self-confidence in transforming individual actions into positive behaviors when solving professional problems (Wardat et al., 2023; Chupradit et al., 2022; Ravindran et al., 2021).

Organizational Performance

According to the study conducted by Reid (2016), in the past, courses in introductory psychology, behavior analysis, and college study skills have been offered at the university or college level according to the principles of behavioral psychology.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Tayco (2022) mentioned that managers and supervisors of the hotel industry in the Philippines share that they experience 21-40% turnover and absenteeism rate of their employees, that the level of productivity of their employees

is good, that their goals were substantially above average, that there was a higher profit/surplus on their financial performance in the previous 12 months and as compared to the previous year.

The results are consistent with the findings of Ashton (2018), who said that HRM practices in the industry are management tools that contribute to the success of the organization. It is associated with positive organizational outcomes like lower turnover intentions, higher levels of productivity and quality, better service performance, better safety performance, enhanced financial performance, and higher organizational performance (Whitman et al., 2012).

Productivity

HRM outcomes list to serve as a practical tool for investigating the HRM productivity within the HR results. HR exercise can be categorized under three domains such as traditional, transactional, and transformational (Kavanagh & Johnson, 2017).

Moreover, this extensive study discussed that employees rewarded for their hard work are more likely to share knowledge. Thus, the knowledge-sharing human-resource management motivates employees, indirectly enhancing productivity (Foss et al., 2015).

Likewise, Zubielqui et al. (2017) found that modern HRM practices have moderate importance when it comes to innovativeness and company performance. The study concludes that HRM is positively correlated to organizational innovation, enhanced strategy innovation, and overall organizational performance (Farouk et al., 2016).

Further, in research conducted by Mallén et al. (2015), it was pointed out that excellent HRM organizations positively influence their capability to learn and improve business strategy outcomes.

However, this literature rarely proposes approaches for developing effective organizational performance measurement and management systems (Sardi et al., 2020).

Although several researchers have underlined the need to further investigate the role of HRM in the PMM domain (Smith & Bititci, 2017), to date, no scholar or practitioner has developed an effectively integrated view that applies a dual approach equally based on HRM in PMM research conventions.

Furthermore, Robbins (2016) mentioned that communication helps develop motivation by explaining to employees what to do, how well they work, and what can be done to improve substandard performance.

Commitment

In earlier studies by Morin et al. (2015), commitment at both organizational and occupational levels was found. Occupational commitment in the context of the teaching profession is significant, as it helps predict one's intention to quit the teaching profession.

Also, Rani et al. (2020) revealed that employees with high work involvement will show positive behavior during work so that company goals and success can be achieved.

Alternatively, faculty's support, financial rewards, fringe benefits, and salaries are very low to attract highly qualified candidates in contrast to the increased living cost (Ahmed et al., 2016).

Employee perceptions of HCHRM will likely be reflected through appropriate attitudes and behaviors, including job satisfaction, affective commitment, and retention intention (Schopman et al., 2015).

Further, Yahaya and Ebrahim (2016) mentioned that an absence of consistency in the meaning of commitment had been observed in the literature, which led to confusion about the true concept of OC.

Furthermore, the research of Oh, Blau, Han, and Kim (2017) considered the perceived organizational value as a mediating variable in their study. It revealed that those employees working with chief HR officers with top levels of human capital are likely to have higher levels of commitment to HR and positively impact the managers' commitment plus behavior. Lastly, Mackay (2018) indicated that the solid significant correlation exists between employee job satisfaction with the high commitment HR practices (which includes training opportunities, feedback opportunities, etc).

Methodology

Research Design

The study used descriptive correlational and causal-comparative design. Descriptive correlational design is used in research studies that aim to provide static pictures of situations and establish the relationship between different variables (McBurney & White, 2009).

Causal-comparative research attempts to identify a causative relationship between an independent variable and dependent variables. Also, the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable is usually a suggested relationship, not proven, because you, the researcher, do not have complete control over the independent variable (Maheshwari, 2018).

This research was about identifying, weighing, and learning whether the role of human resource officers, strategic planning, and work

engagement affect the organizational performance in selected private higher education institutions in Cagayan de Oro City. Questionnaires were hand-given to the respondents to absorb the possible related response rate. To minimize the frustrations of the respondents. Hence, the number of uncompleted questionnaires was limited.

Respondents

Respondents are currently employed in the educational sector in the selected schools in Cagayan de Oro City, either faculty or staff. The researcher conducted a stratified random sampling which involves handpicking of the respondents, usually to suit particular intentions regarding the study. Researchers divide a population into homogeneous subpopulations called strata based on specific characteristics (Thomas, 2020).

The researcher employed the Raosoft Formula to get the sample from the total population 754. The breakdown of respondents are the following: 82 for Capitol University, 71 for Cagayan de Oro College – PHINMA, 8 for Golden Heritage Polytechnic College, 25 for Southern de Oro Philippines College, 28 for Pilgrim Christian College, 13 for STI College, 11 for Blessed Mother College, 9 for AMA Computer College, and 8 for Informatics Institute-Cagayan de Oro. A total of 255 actual respondents in the study will be randomly selected employing a face-to-face visit in conducting the survey. Clarifications from the respondents about the questionnaire were answered directly by the researcher.

Table 1. *Positions Held by the Respondents*

Positions Held by the Respondents	CU	COC	GHPC	SPC	PCC	STIC	BMC	AMA	INFORMATICS	TOTAL
Full-Time Staff	54	46	5	15	10	8	8	6	6	158
Full-Time Faculty	28	25	3	10	18	5	3	3	2	97
Total	82	71	8	25	28	13	11	9	8	255

Instrument

The instrument was a researcher's made questionnaire, which was constructed with several parts. The first part details the level of awareness of the role of the human resource officer in terms of the hiring process, cultural growth, and organizational support. The next part details the level of implementation of strategic planning in terms of performance analysis, development marketing, and tracking progress. The third part investigates the level of work engagement in terms of physical, cognitive, and emotional. The final part investigates the level of organizational performance in terms of productivity and commitment. The instrument responded to a five-point Likert's Scale of (5) Strongly Agree, (4) Agree, (3) Neutral, (2) Disagree, (1) Strongly Disagree.

Procedure

Responses were then coded, tallied, and collated in tables for purposes of statistical treatment and data analysis. Proper scaling was also used for the independent variables. To complete the 102-item questionnaire, the respondents took approximately 15 minutes to answer. Also, the researcher employed a face-to-face survey with the respondents to gather personal information.

The researcher has chosen the full-time faculty and staff of the selected higher education institutions to be the respondents of this research. The data collection will be conducted to 267 out of 863 total population among the identified higher education institutions in Cagayan de Oro City in the School Year 2023-2024. The study was done through the utilization of a survey questionnaire to the full-time faculty and staff. Respondents are currently employed in the educational sector in the different schools in Cagayan de Oro City and may not handle the same position/s.

Participation in this study was purely voluntary and wholehearted. The decision of whether or not to participate does not affect the current relationship with other faculty, staff, and other stakeholders in the institution. Respondents cannot participate in the study without consequences in return. If they wish to withdraw before the data is collected, the data will be returned, disposed of, or destroyed for confidentiality purposes.

Only the researcher of the study, the adviser, the statistician, and the person who is part of the data collection have access to the results of the actual survey. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act (DPA) of 2012 and Its Implementing Rules and Regulations effective since September 8, 2016, the responses to this actual survey will be stored and treated with complete confidentiality and anonymity. The actual survey results were pooled for the research study, and individual results of this study remained confidential.

Data Analysis

Average mean and frequency were used. The data were presented to the statistician for further scrutiny of the measurability of the questions. It underwent content validity, wherein the statistician first approved the tool for validity and was advised to proceed to the administration of the survey questionnaire. The results were presented to the adviser and the panelist after the finalization of data collection.

The manuscript underwent content validity from the experts in the field to ensure quality. Adhering to the critical procedures of research ethics and receiving approval from the Research Ethics Review Committee, the methods of data collection strictly adhered to the proper course of action. All procedures and requirements were followed in order to finally present the data to the adviser and research panel for binding approval.

The data gathered were tabulated and statistically treated for analysis and interpretation using statistical measures and treatment. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean, and standard deviation were used in this study to help describe and understand the level and impact of the variables used in the study. Pearson product-moment correlation was employed to assess and identify the relationship between the dependent variable organizational performance and the independent variables such as the role of human resource officer, strategic planning, and work engagement. Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC or PCC) is the most common way of measuring a linear correlation. It is a number between -1 and 1 that measures the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables (Turney, 2022).

Moreover, Multiple Regression was used to predict the value of a variable based on the value of two or more other variables. It estimates the relationship between two or more independent variables and one dependent variable (Bevans, 2023). Hence, the Path Analysis Model (PAM) is a statistical method that enables researchers to explore patterns of influence among variables within a system. It belongs to a group of general linear models that assess how a set of predictor variables affects multiple dependent variables. Path Analysis is a statistical technique for examining relations among observed variables (Wu, 2019).

Results and Discussion

Is there a significant relationship between Organizational Performance, Role of Human Resource Officer, Strategic Planning, and Work Engagement?

Table 2. *Significant Relationship between the Organizational Performances, Role of Human Resource Officer, Strategic Planning, and Work Engagement*

Variables	N	R	P	Interpretation
Hiring Process	247	.240	.000	Significant
Cultural Growth	247	.190	.000	Significant
Organizational Support	247	.083	.192	Not Significant
Awareness	247	.205	.001	Significant
Performance Analysis	247	.194	.002	Significant
Develop Marketing	247	.200	.002	Significant
Track Progress	247	.185	.003	Significant
Implementation	247	.234	.000	Significant
Physical	247	.314	.000	Significant
Cognitive	247	.242	.000	Significant
Emotional	247	.476	.000	Significant
Work Engagement	247	.412	.000	Significant

Legend: $p < .05$ is significant and $p > .05$ is not significant

Table 2 depicts the results of Pearson Correlation analysis for the Significant Relationship between Organizational Performances, the Role of Human Resource Officer, Strategic Planning, and Work Engagement. As seen in the table, organizational support ($p > .05$) has no significant correlation to organizational performance. On one hand, the variables hiring process ($p < .05$), cultural growth ($p < .05$), awareness ($p < .05$), performance analysis ($p < .05$), develop marketing ($p < .05$), track progress ($p < .05$), implementation ($p < .05$), physical ($p < .05$), cognitive ($p < .05$), emotional ($p < .05$), and work engagement ($p < .05$) have statistically significant positive relationship to HR Officers' organizational performance. This means that if these said variables will improve, the HR Officers' organizational performance will also likely to improve.

Khuay et al. (2023) revealed that human resource management can help the organization to elicit and extract knowledge, skill, expertise, talent, and competency of employees to work for the success and growth of the organization. This implies that the organization should train unknowledgeable and unskilled employees to have more knowledge and skills that are required to work for the organization. A study by Olang-o (2018) pointed out that a broadly based participative strategic planning practice can actually make the most of the frequent leadership changes by coupling a new leader's external perspective with a stable core internal group that is committed to mutual goals and a shared vision of a successful future. It suggests that strategic planning intensity is determined by managerial, environmental, and organizational factors, which enhance organizational performance.

Organizational performance has been well affected by the involvement of employees in their work. An employee who is highly engaged with his job is one who pays attention to the work of the organization and presents some kind of initiatives for the benefit of the organization (Narayanamma et al., 2022). It then connotes that engagement and commitment organizational approaches intended to guarantee that employees are dedicated to their organization's objectives and principles, encouraged to donate to organizational success, and are able at the same time to improve their own sense of safety.

Which among the variables, singly or in combination, influence the organizational performance?

Table 2. Multiple Regression Analysis for the variables, singly or in combination, Influence the Organizational Performance

Independent Variables	Coefficients		Coefficients			Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
(Constant)	2.622	.299		8.768	.000	
Hiring Process	.110	.059	.115	1.852	.065	Not Significant
Cultural Growth	.048	.052	.064	.917	.360	Not Significant
Organizational Support	-.081	.057	-.107	1.422	.156	Not Significant
	Unstandardized		Standardized			
Performance Analysis	.032	.042	.054	.764	.446	Not Significant
Develop Marketing	.000	.051	.000	.004	.997	Not Significant
Track Progress	.009	.041	.016	.213	.832	Not Significant
Physical	.070	.075	.089	.930	.353	Not Significant
Emotional	.336	.079	.478	4.27	.000	Significant
Work Engagement	-.096	.128	-.116	-0.750	.454	Not Significant

R= .502 R²= .252 Adjusted R²= .224 F=8.87 P-value=.000
 Legend: p<.05 is significant and p>.05 is not significant

Table 2 presents the results of the computation of Multiple Regression Analysis for the variables, singly or in combination, best predict HR Officers’ organizational performance. As depicted in the table, the R value was .502 signifying a moderate positive relationship between the independent and the dependent variables. The R2 value of .252 implies that the predictor variables used in this study only explained 25.2 % of the variability of HR Officers’ organizational performance. The probability value of p=0.000 (F=8.87) indicates that there was a significant relationship between the HR Officers’ organizational performance, and the predictor variables. Of the nine variables included in the model, hiring process (p>.05), cultural growth (p>.05), organizational support (p>.05), performance analysis (p>.05) develop marketing (p>.05), track progress (p>.05), physical (p>.05), and work engagement (p>.05) statistically failed to predict/influenced HR officers’ organizational performance.

Meanwhile, the variable that best predicts/influences HR officers’ organizational performance is emotional (p<.05) with a beta value of β=4.27.

The regression equation model of this study was $Y' = 2.622 + .336X1$

Where

Y' = HR Officers’ Organizational Performance 2.622 = is the B constant

$X1$ = Work Engagement in terms of Emotional

The regression equation implies that the HR Officers’ Organizational performance was significantly influenced/predicted by the work engagement of HR Officers in terms of the emotional component. As to the extent of the direct effect of the said variable to HR Officers’ Organizational performance, for every one-point increase of emotional component, the HR Officers’ organizational performance will have an increase of .336.

Emotional engagement leads to higher job satisfaction and job performance; emotional engagement is associated with increased work engagement levels, which in turn enhances productivity and promotes a sense of balance and consideration towards others, leading to increased willingness to work better and be more productive (Barreiro, 2020).

It insinuates that emotional engagement contributes to positive individual and organizational outcomes, including increased job satisfaction, commitment, productivity, and employee well-being.

Conclusions

The respondents in this study underscored the pivotal role of the environment in shaping awareness of the human resource officer's role, emphasizing the need for a thorough evaluation of hiring processes to enhance the organizational performance of higher education institutions.

Furthermore, respondents highlighted the significance of employee initiatives in implementing strategic planning, indicating that meeting organizational expectations contributes to individual and institutional performance.

Additionally, respondents inferred that the physical environment significantly impacts employee work engagement, particularly after comprehending departmental and institutional goals and objectives.

The statements provided by the respondents regarding the level of organizational performance suggest that participation, commitment,

and productivity directly influence the performance of employees, thereby affecting the overall quality of work performance among staff, faculty, and administration within educational institutions.

The findings, conclusions, and implications of this study summed up some key points to be carried out for future use. Here are the following recommendations:

The first recommendation is for the academic institutions to be continually on the less influential sub-variables towards organizational performance and enhance the emotional engagement of the stakeholders to strengthen the work engagement as well the performance leading to the improvements of the institutions. Also, results emphasized that an improved institutional awareness of the employees' emotional intelligence may be brought to discussions with the administration creating a well-crafted tool which may benefit both employees and the employer.

The second recommendation is for the faculty and staff to consider organizational performance benefiting the students, faculty, and staff to improve the institution in giving quality service to its stakeholders. Based on the evidence of the study and current literature on organizational performance, it is recommended that faculty-staff as well as the employer- employee associations may be established to guide the academic success to change for the betterment of the relationship between the interests of both the employer and its employees.

The third recommendation is for the human resource officers to continually provide work opportunities for all its employees, helping everyone to build a better understanding of work dynamics, leading to positive work performance. Evidence from this study resulted in the recommendation that workforce relationships be built into the general welfare of the employees in the institution to reflect on individual interests and abilities relating to the workforce's needs.

The fourth recommendation is for the board directors and owners to continually build in-depth strategic planning to boost the morale of the employees as well as help the institutions stop the increasing employee turnover, leading to the lifelong commitment of the workforce. Evidence from this study resulted in the recommendation that the administration may encourage the HR officer to propose a continuous development an emotional intelligence programs and seminars improve the social-emotional awareness of the employees, leading to a well-developed self-control and interpersonal skills, which are vital to organizational performance of institutions.

The fifth recommendation is for future researchers to consider further studies by using other sub-variables which would help identify discoveries about what factors greatly influence organizational performance. Also, the results led the researcher with the recommendation that choosing different variables and identifying new settings may give additional discoveries and knowledge, leading researchers to dive into what makes employees enhance strategic planning, organizational learning, work engagement, and the role of human resource officers affect the emotional of the employees' performance.

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